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Scientific Research Techniques: Critical Error Vectors, Human Factors, and Metacognitive Management

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Abstract

Various systemic errors are identified in scientific research praxis, which hinder the integrity of the results obtained. Through qualitative analysis and the study of significant historical cases, such as that of Albert Einstein and his unjustified reasons for erroneously introducing the cosmological constant into his equations, the impact on the validation of theories produced by psychological variables inherent in the human factor that compromise the necessary absolute objectivity is demonstrated. The replication crisis highlights how scientific progress is limited by different critical vectors of distortion, including a lack of skeptical thinking, confirmation bias, traditionalisms, the fallacy of instrumental rigor, dogmatic isolation in the face of refutation, and the prevalence of extrinsic goals over discoveries. Metacognitive management is determined to be essential in the research community.

Introduction

Although it may seem incoherent, a major obstacle to research has always been the human factor, the researchers themselves, brilliant and motivated minds but prisoners of their own desires and beliefs, not being totally objective about their own work and limiting the progress of their discoveries.

Albert Einstein and the Cosmological Constant

Albert Einstein, one of the most privileged minds of our era. The most important scientific achievement of his life was the development of the theory of relativity, first the special, and finally the general. He came to various conclusions, one of which was that the universe could not be static, as had been believed until then. Then, for no logical reason other than a simple refusal to detach himself from his traditional ideas instilled in his mind by the physics known up to that point, he introduced what he called the cosmological constant into his own equations so that they could justify a static universe. It may seem that I am providing a very simple explanation of Einstein's motive for introducing this constant, but the truth is that, conceptually, that was the only reason. A simple mathematical resource, an anti-gravitational force, to give space-time an intrinsic tendency to expand, justifying that it exactly balances the attraction of all matter in the universe, making a static universe possible. However, this hypothetical term was neither required by the theory itself, nor was it justified from a theoretical point of view.

Later, due to observations made by astronomer Edwin Hubble, Einstein declared that the introduction of the cosmological constant was the "biggest blunder" he had ever made in his life. This fact is not relevant, nor is the fact that, in the future, this constant would find some sense. What really matters is that Einstein introduced the cosmological constant

into his equations unjustifiably, only to adapt them to the traditionalism with which he had grown up. Einstein was not really objective about his own results, despite not finding any fault in them. His previous beliefs imprisoned one of the most brilliant minds of our time, limiting his work. A genius committing a perfectly human mistake, which he later wisely admitted and retracted. This is not the case for all scientists; some never admit to being wrong and continue to seek flimsy explanations to support their theories, while others proclaim to have defended the incorrect approach only to demonstrate its inconsistency.

Research Results

It is also very common for the researcher to be influenced by the results they wish to obtain a priori. Unconsciously, they find themselves, adapting the facts to the theories, giving greater importance to the positively expected results, even going so far as to force them. Therefore, in this case, the scientist is not objective in their research and does not seek to draw conclusions through reasoning based on impartially obtained results. On the contrary, they pursue to obtain evidence for a conclusion they have longed for from the outset. Their desires are their self-imposed limitation.

Tools for Research

Another error is to place more value on research tools than on the research itself and its purpose. Researchers sometimes get lost in various advanced statistical methods, computer programs, interpolation and differential problem-solving techniques, matrix calculus, simulation and process analysis models, etc., forgetting that these are simply tools for a purpose and not an end in themselves. They justify the methods and become wrapped up in them, with useless nuances and interpretations, forgetting what they set

out to investigate. No progress is made in achieving new discoveries, but rather, a stagnation occurs along the way by justifying simple tools already proven. The lack of method is their mistake.

Scientific Method

Skeptical thinking is the basis of the scientific method. If scientific skepticism is not used, serious errors are committed. Arguments from authority are dogmatically accepted, forgetting that authorities (experts would be a more realistic term) have made mistakes and will make them again. The method of alternative working hypotheses is not used; on the contrary, some researchers stick with the evidence that best fits their predetermined ideas instead of looking for evidence that can withstand any refutation. An argument is taken as true if most of its components are true, forgetting that they must all work. These are just a few examples of a lack of skeptical thinking, among many others.

Theories and Refutation

It is nonsense to take it personally when one's own theory is questioned, when it should be the opposite, since if it withstands any attack from every point of view, it is the best proof of its veracity. In 1993, Joseph Taylor and Russell Hulse jointly received the Nobel Prize in Physics for challenging General Relativity with their hypothesis on binary pulsars, ultimately obtaining confirmation of Einstein's theory with their results. If something resists any attempt to prove it wrong, any refutation, it is the best proof of its certainty. Although that was not Taylor and Hulse's goal, and it is also true that General Relativity is not consistent at the quantum level, the example seems clear to me.

Awards

The most obvious error, but perhaps the most common, is to conduct research in order to gain recognition, financial rewards, and other useless baggage for a logical mind. In this case, we lose sight of the true objective of our work, which is a serious impediment to its development. We must be sufficiently motivated to fill ourselves with passion and enthusiasm for obtaining new knowledge and discoveries. Once we have achieved our goal, we are filled with happiness at having done so and at sharing it with others, which is truly the best reward.

Conclusion

In short, a good researcher should have a free mind, not imprisoned by beliefs, traditionalisms, preconceived ideas, desires, prides, and other personal limitations that delay or even impede an objective result. I am not trying to criticize here, I am simply stating that we are human and we make these kinds of mistakes. But it is absurd to assume that it is normal to make them, and foolishness to proudly deny them. On the contrary, it is wise to recognize them and eradicate them.

Note: I published this essay in May 2010 in Knol – A Unit of Knowledge (Google Inc.) with ID: 24dyy1s94pur1/6. I have republished it in 2026, with its original content completely intact, without any modifications. It has been verified that everything stated remains fully valid (time has only confirmed this), even with an upward trend. As an example, the replication crisis (in which the critical vectors I identified were decisive), a term coined in 2012 and confirmed in 2015, is a source of concern in the scientific community and society in general. Metacognitive management, as a self-audit of the thought process, is absolutely necessary in research praxis as a guarantee of rigor and

replicability. With the exponential growth of Artificial Intelligence and its massive use in research, the warnings in this essay are more necessary than ever.ⁱ

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ⁱ The publication in Knol in May 2010 can be viewed in the Internet Archive (Wayback Machine) using the original link: <http://knol.google.com/k/josé-ángel-gómez-fernández/investigación-científica/24dyy1s94pur1/6>. The content of the essay in 2026 is exactly the same as the original from 2010, with no modifications (although I have made a slight change to the title, which in 2010, was aimed at the general public of the aforementioned platform).